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COMPARING VARIOUS CHANNEL ESTIMATION TECHNIQUES FOR OFDM SYSTEMS USING MATLAB

Raghad K. Mohammed, Department of Basic Sciences, College of Dentistry
University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

ABSTRACT

This paper compares the performance of various channel estimation techniques for OFDM systems over quasi-static channels using MATLAB. It compares the performance of five channel estimation techniques, these are: decision directed (DD), linear interpolation, second-order interpolation, discrete Fourier transform (DFT) interpolation, minimum mean square error (MMSE) interpolation. The performance is evaluated in terms of two widely-used performance measures, namely, bit-error rate (BER) and the mean square error (MSE) for different levels of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The OFDM model is explained and implemented using MATLAB to run different simulations. The simulation results demonstrate that the DD channel estimation provides the lowest BER and MSE as compared to interpolation techniques, at the cost of extra processing delay and comparatively sensitive to channel variations between OFDM symbols. Also, the MMSE interpolation outperforms all other interpolation techniques.

KEYWORDS

OFDM, pilot-based channel estimation, pilot allocation, direct decision, interpolation channel estimation, LS, MMSE, MATLAB.

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AUTHOR

Raghad K. Mohammed is serving as a member of academic staff at the Department of Basic Sciences, College of Dentistry, University of Baghdad (Baghdad, Iraq). She received her B.Sc degree in Computer Science from the Department of Computer science, Al-Rafidain University College (Baghdad, Iraq) in 2003, and her M.Sc degree in Computer Networks, Informatics Institute for Higher Studies, University of Technology (Baghdad, Iraq) in 2005. Her research interests include cryptography and steganography, image processing, and information and network security.

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DIFFERENT TRUST BASED ROUTING SCHEMES IN MANET

Mousumi Sardar¹ and Koushik Majumder²

Department of Computer Science & Engineering, West Bengal University of Technology,
Kolkata, India

ABSTRACT

A mobile ad hoc network is a wireless network in which no infrastructure is available. MANET is a selfconfiguring network. Due to dynamic nature of MANET it is very challenging work to employ a secure route. The intermediate nodes cooperate with each other as there is no such base station or access point. The routing protocols play important role in transferring data. Cryptographic mechanisms are used in routing protocols to secure data packets while transmitted in the network. But cryptographic techniques incur a high computational cost and can't identify the nodes with malicious intention. So, employing cryptographic techniques in MANET are quite impractical as MANETs have limited resource and vulnerable to several security attacks. Trust mechanism is used as an alternative to cryptographic technique. Trust mechanism secures data forwarding by isolating nodes with malicious intention using trust value on the nodes. In this paper we survey different trust based protocols of MANET and compare their performances.

KEYWORDS

Network Protocols, Wireless Network, Mobile Network, Virus, Worms & Trojon

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AUTHORS

Mousumi Sardar has received her B.Tech degree in Information Technology in the year 2011 from College of Engineering & Management, Kolaghat, India. She is now perusing her M.Tech. degree in Information Technology from West Bengal University of Technology Kolkata, India.

Koushik Majumder has received his B.Tech and M.Tech degrees in Computer Science and Engineering and Information Technology in the year 2003 and 2005 respectively from University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India. He obtained his PhD degree in the field of Mobile Ad Hoc Networking in 2012 from Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India. Before coming to the teaching profession he has worked in reputed international software organizations like Tata Consultancy Services and Cognizant Technology Solutions. He is presently working as an Assistant Professor in the Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering in West Bengal University of Technology, Kolkata, India He has published several papers in International and National level journals and conferences. He is a Senior Member, IEEE.

A PRACTICAL ROUTE RECONSTRUCTION METHOD FOR WI-FI MESH NETWORKS IN DISASTER SITUATION WITH SPARE AP

Erdenetuya Dorj¹, Jovilyn Fajardo² and Kazuhiko Kinoshita³

¹Department of Information Science and Intelligent Systems, Tokushima University,
Japan

²Space-Time Engineering LLC, Japan

³Graduate School of Technology, Industrial and Social Science, Tokushima University,
Japan

ABSTRACT

Computer networks comprise essential infrastructure in modern society and must function even in a disaster situation. Therefore, fault-tolerant networks are being actively studied. Disaster information systems, however, suffer from two main issues: lack of their utilization in peacetime and the difficulty for a non-expert to manage them should a disaster strike. Therefore, we place special emphasis on the development of a reliable network infrastructure that can function during both normal and disaster times, using a Wi-Fi-based wireless mesh network. In a large-scale disaster situation, our goal is to identify a way to reconstruct the mesh network by adding the minimum number of spare access points (APs) to ensure the reachability of all mesh routers to the backbone network. Furthermore, we consider that only public workers without any experience with wireless communication technologies must decide upon the adequate locations for spare APs and install them. Both of simulation experiments and field trial prove the effectiveness of the proposed methods.

KEYWORDS

Wi-Fi, wireless mesh network, disaster, rerouting

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AUTHORS

Erdenetuya Dorj

She received her B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in Information Network from Mongolian University of Science and Technology, Mongolia, in 2007, and 2008, respectively. She is currently pursuing a Ph.D. degree in Information Science and Intelligent Systems at Tokushima University, Japan. Her academic interests include wireless multi-hop mesh network, QoS in Internet of Things.

Jovilyn Therese B. Fajardo

She received her B.S. degrees in Chemistry and Computer Engineering from Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines in 2006 and 2007, respectively. She also received her M.S. in Electronics Engineering from the same university in 2010. She then received her D.Eng degree in Information Science from Nara Institute of Science and Technology in 2013, and joined Nagoya University as a Designated Assistant Professor from 2014 to 2017. Currently, she is working as an engineer at Space-Time Engineering Japan.

Kazuhiko Kinoshita

He received the B. E., M. E. and Ph. D degrees in information systems engineering from Osaka University, Osaka, Japan, in 1996, 1997 and 2003, respectively. From April 1998 to March 2002, he was an Assistant Professor at the Department of Information Systems Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Osaka University. From April 2002 to March 2008, he was an Assistant Professor at the Department of Information Networking, Graduate School of Information Science and Technology, Osaka University. From April 2008 to January 2015, he was an Associate Professor at the same University. Since February 2015, he has been a Professor at Tokushima University. His research interests include mobile networks, network management, and agent communications. Dr. Kinoshita is a member of IEEE and a senior member of IEICE.

ENERGY EFFICIENT HIERARCHICAL CLUSTER HEAD ELECTION USING EXPONENTIAL DECAY FUNCTION PREDICTION

Ojoawo A.O and Adeniji O.D Computer Science Department, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

In the recent years, wireless sensor network (WSN) have witnessed increased interest in information gathering in applications such as combat field reconnaissance, security surveillance, environmental monitoring, patient health monitoring and so on. Thus, there is a need for scalable and energy-efficient routing, data gathering and aggregation protocols in these WSN environments. Various hierarchical clustering Protocols have been proposed by authors for WSN to improve system stability, lifetime, and energy efficiency. Clustering involves grouping nodes into disjoint and non-overlapping clusters. In this paper we motivate the need for clustering. Secondly, we present general classification of published clustering schemes. Thirdly, we review some existing clustering algorithms proposed for WSNs; highlighting their objectives, features, and so on. Finally, we develop an Average Energy (AvE) prediction algorithm using exponential decay function $y=Ae^{-ax}+B$. We then combine this function with the probabilistic distributed LEACH of algorithm to determine suitable CHs. The combined algorithm was implemented on MATLAB simulator and tested for homogenous network. The result gathered from the simulation shows that the extended algorithm in homogenous network mode is able to achieve 39% stability, 11% Average energy Dissipation per round and 40% Lifespan better than LEACH-Homo. This paper proposes a new direction in improving energy efficiency of WSN routing protocol, which is desirable in some critical WSN applications. .

KEYWORDS

Wireless sensors networks, Clustering, Routing, sensor node, Average Energy, round, exponential decay curve

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AUTHORS

Ojoawo, Akinwale Olusola received his B.Tech Degree from Ladoke Akintola University of Technologies, LAUTECH, Ogbomoso, in 2001. He has just concluded his M.Sc Computer Science at University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Nigeria. He is currently lecturing at Computer science department, The Ibarapa Polytechnic, Eruwa, Nigeria. He has a number of publications in various national/international journals and conferences. His current research areas are wireless sensor network and mobile ad hoc network.

POSITION ESTIMATION OF AUTONOMOUS UNDERWATER SENSORS USING THE VIRTUAL LONG BASELINE METHOD

Alexander Dikarev, Stanislav Dmitriev, Vitaliy Kubkin and Andrey Vasilenko

Underwater communication & navigation laboratory, LLC, Moscow, Russia

ABSTRACT

This article contains a description of a mathematical model of an acoustic system for positioning autonomous underwater sensors using the virtual long base method, which can be used during the vessel's collection of information over the deployed underwater network of autonomous sensors (underwater wireless sensors network), during the initial determination of the geographical position of the bottom long baseline elements or search, including cooperative, with the use of a swarm of autonomous surface vehicles (UASV) of emergency submerged objects equipped with an emergency beacon (for example, aircraft and ships); The article provides a scheme of an experimental set of equipment, as well as a description of the conducted field experiments and their results.

KEYWORDS

Underwater positioning system, VLBL, underwater wireless sensor network, emergency beacon positioning

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AUTHORS

Alexander Dikarev

received his M.Eng in Launching equipment of rockets and cosmic apparatus from Volgograd Technical State University, Russia. He has 10 years experience in underwater acoustic communication and navigation system design and development: in Research Institute of Hydroacoustic Communications (Volgograd, Russia), The University Of Manchester (UK), now he is R&D Director in Underwater communication & Navigation laboratory (Moscow, Russia)

Stanislav Dmitriev

received his M.Sc in Radiophysics in Volgograd State University, Russia. He has 10 years of experience in Underwater Acoustic communication & navigation system design & development: in Research Insitute of Hydroacoustic Communications (Volgograd, Russia), now he is Engineering Director in Underwater Communication & Navigation laboratory (Moscow, Russia)

Vitaliy Kubkin

received his M.Eng in Volgograd Technical State University, Russia. He has 10 years of experience in Underwater Acoustic communication & navigation system design & development: in Research Insitute of Hydroacoustic Communications (Volgograd, Russia), now he is Senior Researcher in Underwater Communication & Navigation laboratory (Moscow, Russia)

Andrey Vasilenko

Received his M.Sc in Radiophysics in Volgograd State University, Russia. He has more than 15 years of experience in Underwater Acoustic communication & navigation system design & development: in Research Insitute of Hydroacoustic Communications (Volgograd, Russia), now he is Chief Electronics Engineer in Underwater Communication & Navigation laboratory (Moscow, Russia)

EMERGING WIRELESS TECHNOLOGIES IN THE INTERNET OF THINGS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Mahmoud Elkhodr, Seyed Shahrestani and Hon Cheung
School of Computing, Engineering and Mathematics, Western Sydney
University, Sydney,
Australia

ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) incorporates multiple long-range, short-range, and personal area wireless networks and technologies into the designs of IoT applications. This enables numerous business opportunities in fields as diverse as e-health, smart cities, smart homes, among many others. This research analyses some of the major evolving and enabling wireless technologies in the IoT. Particularly, it focuses on ZigBee, 6LoWPAN, Bluetooth Low Energy, LoRa, and the different versions of Wi-Fi including the recent IEEE 802.11ah protocol. The studies evaluate the capabilities and behaviours of these technologies regarding various metrics including the data range and rate, network size, RF Channels and Bandwidth, and power consumption. It is concluded that there is a need to develop a multifaceted technology approach to enable interoperable and secure communications in the IoT.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things, Wireless Technologies, Low-power, M2M Communications.

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AUTHORS

Dr. Mahmoud Elkhodr is with the School of Computing, Engineering and Mathematics at Western Sydney University (Western), Australia. He has been awarded the International Postgraduate Research Scholarship (IPRS) and Australian Postgraduate Award (APA) in 2012-2015. Mahmoud has been awarded the High Achieving Graduate Award in 2011 as well. His research interests include: Internet of Things, e-health, Human Computer Interactions, Security and Privacy.

Dr. Seyed Shahrestani completed his PhD degree in Electrical and Information Engineering at the University of Sydney. He joined Western Sydney University (Western) in 1999, where he is currently a Senior Lecturer. He is also the head of the Networking, Security and Cloud Research (NSCR) group at Western. His main teaching and research interests include: computer networking, management and security of networked systems, analysis, control and management of complex systems, artificial intelligence applications, and health ICT. He is also highly active in higher degree research training supervision, with successful results.

Dr. Hon Cheung graduated from The University of Western Australia in 1984 with First Class Honours in Electrical Engineering. He received his PhD degree from the same university in 1988. He was a lecturer in the Department of Electronic Engineering, Hong Kong Polytechnic from 1988 to 1990. From 1990 to 1999, he was a lecturer in Computer Engineering at Edith Cowan University, Western Australia. He has been a senior lecturer in Computing at Western Sydney University since 2000. Dr Cheung has research experience in a number of areas, including conventional methods in artificial intelligence, fuzzy sets, artificial neural networks, digital signal processing, image processing, network security and forensics, and communications and networking. In the area of teaching, Dr Cheung has experience in development and delivery of a relative large number of subjects in computer science, electrical and electronic engineering, computer engineering and networking.

SIMULATION AND VERIFICATION TWO YAGI-UDI AND S-BAND SATELLITE DISH GROUND STATION ANTENNAS FOR LEO NANOSATELLITES COMMUNICATIONS

Vahid Rastinasab And Victor Hu

¹ Department of Electrical and Information, BIT, Beijing, China

²Department of Electrical and Information, BIT, Beijing, China

ABSTRACT

Ground station antennas are a part of TTC system, generally, Yagi-Udi antennas and Parabola dish antenna are using in Earth segment to communicate with LEO small satellites, this paper uniquely presents the three huge antennas of a ground station which are communicating with some microsattellites with view window above Beijing, China. The ground station contains two Yagi-Udi antennas for VHF/UHF and an S-band dish antenna for reception of payloads data. For verification feasibility of the antennas, simulations have been accomplished according to the antennas requirements. Eventually, the simulations assisted to recognize the matched commercial ground station antennas based on comparison of the simulations with commercial antennas and the matched ones are chosen for the implementation on the ground station.

KEYWORDS

Amateur radio antenna, Telemetry and Tracking, Yagi-Udi antenna, parabolic dish antenna, ground station antennas.

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AUTHORS

Vahid Rastinasab, Master Student at BUAA, China. His interests are satellite communication and RF circuits. His paper achieved 2nd prize at international colligate space craft innovative design contest, HIT 2018, China. He implemented a VHF/UHF transceiver for a nanosatellite with 500 Km altitude in his M.Sc duration. Recently, he's interested in prospecting of asteroids using CubeSats and he is going to continue his research direction in deep space communication.

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF LOCAL ANCHOR BASED 5G HETNETS USING STOCHASTIC GEOMETRY

Eren Balevi and Richard D. Gitlin

Department of Electrical Engineering, University of South Florida
Tampa, Florida 33620, USA

ABSTRACT

In heterogeneous 5G networks (HetNets) a local anchor node ensures coordination among small cell low power nodes (LPNs). User equipment (UE) that cannot directly reach the local anchor node will transmit and receive data through LPN. To facilitate measurement of the interference power for this 2-hop hierarchical network topology, a total distance distribution between a UE and a local anchor is derived as a closed form expression in terms of hypergeometric functions. This distribution can be directly utilized in the interference power and outage probability analysis. Numerical results show that the interference power can be tightly approximated using the derived distribution for large distances, which significantly eases the outage probability analysis.

KEYWORDS

Stochastic geometry, interference analysis, two-tier networks, local anchor.

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AUTHORS

Eren Balevi received the B.S., M.S., and Ph.D. degrees in Electrical and Electronics Engineering from Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Turkey, in 2008, 2010 and 2016 respectively. He is currently a postdoctoral scholar in the Electrical Engineering Department at University of South Florida. His current research interests are in the general areas of 5G wireless systems and the Internet of Things in addition to the general areas of molecular communications, multi-user wireless communications and signal processing.

Richard D. Gitlin is a State of Florida 21st Century World Class Scholar, Distinguished University Professor and the Agere Systems Chaired Distinguished Professor of Electrical Engineering at the University of South Florida. He has more than 45 years of leadership in the communications and networking industry. He was at Bell Labs/Lucent Technologies for 32-years performing and leading pioneering research and development in digital communications, broadband networking, and wireless systems. Dr. Gitlin was Senior VP for Communications and Networking Research at Bell Labs and later CTO of Lucent's Data Networking Business Unit. After retiring from Lucent, he was visiting professor of Electrical Engineering at Columbia University, where he supervised several doctoral students and research projects and then Chief Technology Officer of Hammerhead Systems, a venture funded networking company in Silicon Valley. Since joining USF in 2008, he has focused on the intersection of communications with medicine and created an interdisciplinary team that is focused on wireless networking of in vivo miniature wirelessly controlled devices to advance minimally invasive surgery and other cyber-physical health care systems. Dr. Gitlin has also directed research on advancing wireless local and 4G and 5G cellular systems by increasing their reliability and capacity. Dr. Gitlin is a member of the National Academy of Engineering (NAE), a Fellow of the IEEE, a Bell Laboratories Fellow, and a Charter Fellow of the National Academy of Inventors (NAI). He is also a co-recipient of the 2005 Thomas Alva Edison Patent Award and the S.O. Rice prize, has co-authored a text, published ~150 papers and holds 55 patents.

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Mahmoud Elkhodr, Seyed Shahrestani and Hon Cheung

School of Computing, Engineering and Mathematics, Western Sydney University,
Sydney, Australia

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The Internet of Things (IoT) incorporates multiple long-range, short-range, and personal area wireless networks and technologies into the designs of IoT applications. This enables numerous business opportunities in fields as diverse as e-health, smart cities, smart homes, among many others. This research analyses some of the major evolving and enabling wireless technologies in the IoT. Particularly, it focuses on ZigBee, 6LoWPAN, Bluetooth Low Energy, LoRa, and the different versions of Wi-Fi including the recent IEEE 802.11ah protocol. The studies evaluate the capabilities and behaviours of these technologies regarding various metrics including the data range and rate, network size, RF Channels and Bandwidth, and power consumption. It is concluded that there is a need to develop a multifaceted technology approach to enable interoperable and secure communications in the IoT.

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AUTHORS

Dr. Mahmoud Elkhodr is with the School of Computing, Engineering and Mathematics at Western Sydney University (Western), Australia. He has been awarded the International Postgraduate Research Scholarship (IPRS) and Australian Postgraduate Award (APA) in 2012-2015. Mahmoud has been awarded the High Achieving Graduate Award in 2011 as well. His research interests include: Internet of Things, e-health, Human Computer Interactions, Security and Privacy.

Dr. Seyed Shahrestani completed his PhD degree in Electrical and Information Engineering at the University of Sydney. He joined Western Sydney University (Western) in 1999, where he is currently a Senior Lecturer. He is also the head of the Networking, Security and Cloud Research (NSCR) group at Western. His main teaching and research interests include: computer networking, management and security of networked systems, analysis, control and management of complex systems, artificial intelligence applications, and health ICT. He is also highly active in higher degree research training supervision, with successful results.

Dr. Hon Cheung graduated from The University of Western Australia in 1984 with First Class Honours in Electrical Engineering. He received his PhD degree from the same university in 1988. He was a lecturer in the Department of Electronic Engineering, Hong Kong Polytechnic from 1988 to 1990. From 1990 to 1999, he was a lecturer in Computer Engineering at Edith Cowan University, Western Australia. He has been a senior lecturer in Computing at Western Sydney University since 2000. Dr Cheung has research experience in a number of areas, including conventional methods in artificial intelligence, fuzzy sets, artificial neural networks, digital signal processing, image processing, network security and forensics, and communications and networking. In the area of teaching, Dr Cheung has experience in development and delivery of a relative large number of subjects in computer science, electrical and electronic engineering, computer engineering and networking.

IMPLEMENTATION OF A NEW IR-UWB SYSTEM BASED ON M-OAM MODULATION ON FPGA COMPONENT

K. Hamidoun^{1;2}, R. SADLI², Y. Elhillali², R. Ellassali¹, A. Rivenq²
And K. Elbaamrani¹
1UCA, ENSA, TIM, Marrakech, Morocco
2UVHC, IEMN-DOAE, F-59313 Valenciennes, France

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the implementation of an Impulse Radio Ultra Wide Band (IR-UWB) communication system based on Orthogonal Amplitude Modulation (OAM) on the FPGA board (Field Programmable Gate Array). The Orthogonal Amplitude Modulation is a new modulation technique that provides a high data rate transmission, using the orthogonal waveforms named MGF (Modified Gegenbauer Function). In this work, the FPGA card and the converters DAC (Digital-to-Analog Converter) and ADC (Analog to Digital Converter) are considered to perform the implementation. The system is running in the simulation field and in the real system on the hardware equipment. The obtained results show that the implementation of UWBOAM system on FPGA board is running well and provide a high - real time computations system.

KEYWORDS

UWB, FPGA, OAM, ADC, DAC, simulation, real time system

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Authors

Khadija Hamidoun was born in 1987. She was graduated Engineer in 2011 in Telecommunication and Network from the degree in 2016 from Cadi Ayyad University (Morocco) and UVHC University (France). Her primary interest is in signal processing especially Ultrawide band technology applied to intelligent transport systems.

YassinElhillali was born in Chemaia, Morocco, in 1979. He received her Diploma of MS degree in 2002, and then his PhD degree in 2005, from the University of Valenciennes (France). He actually is an Assistant Professor in electronics at this primary interest is signal processing applied to intelligent transportation and telecommunication systems, and their implementations on FPGA computing unit.

Raja Ellassali is a Ph.D. degree in Telecommunications and Computer Science from t Cadi Ayyad University. She received the MS degree in Telecommunication and Networking in 1997 from the ChouaibDoukkali University. Actually, she is a Professor at the ENSA of Marrakech. She is a leader of telecom networks team in TIM laboratory. Her main activity is in intelligent transport systems using UWB Technology and vehicle to vehicle communication (VANET).

AtikaRivenq was graduated Engineer from The ENSIMEV School in 1993, received the M.S. degree in 1993 and then her Ph.D. degree in 1996 from Valenciennes (France). She is Professor in electronics at this university with the IEMN/DOAE Lab. Her main activity is in signal processing applied to intelligent transport systems. She participates at many national and European projects communication and inter-vehicles communication especially using UWB technology

Khalid Elbaamrani received the M.S. degree in electrical Engineering in 2000 and the PhD in 2005 in Telecommunication Engineering from the Cadi Ayyad University, Morocco. He is presently working as Professor at the ENSA of Marrakech. His research interests include digital communication, multiuser information theory, OFDM systems, MIMO-OFDM systems and vehicle to vehicle communication (VANET).

